

BIODT
biodiversitydigitaltwin

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D2.1 - Plan for Dissemination & Exploitation Including Communication Activities

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Glossary of Terms

Item	Description
CSC	CSC – IT Center for Science Ltd
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication
DestinE	Destination Earth
DiSSCo	Distributed System of Scientific Collections (<i>Research Infrastructure</i>)
DoA	Description of Action
DT	Digital Twin
EC	European Commission
eLTER	Integrated European Long-Term Ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological Research (<i>Research Infrastructure</i>)
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union

FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility (<i>Research Infrastructure</i>)
HPC	High-Performance Computing
IT4Innovations	IT4Innovations National Supercomputing Center
KOM	Kick-Off Meeting
KER	Key Exploitable Results
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LifeWatch ERIC	e-Science European Infrastructure for Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research (<i>Research Infrastructure</i>)
M	Month
Naturalis	Naturalis Biodiversity Center
RI	Research Infrastructure
RIA	Research and Innovation Action
SG	Stakeholder Group
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
TNO	The Netherlands Organization for Applied Scientific Research TNO
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
Trust-IT	Trust-IT Srl
WP	Work Package

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Biodiversity, Digital Twin, Modelling, Simulation, Prediction, High-Performance Computing, Artificial Intelligence

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Executive Summary

The Biodiversity Digital Twin (BioDT) project will provide both advanced models for simulation and prediction capabilities, demonstrated through thematic use cases that address critical issues related to global biodiversity dynamics. BioDT will enhance the protection and restoration of Europe's ecosystems and biodiversity by managing natural resources sustainably. This will ensure clean and healthy environments, as well as contribute to increasing food security and sustainability of the food system.

BioDT responds to key EU and international policy initiatives, including the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030, EU Green Deal, UN Sustainable Development Goals, Destination Earth, and exploits scientific and technological excellence at the frontline of European innovation (e.g. LUMI Supercomputer).

This deliverable presents the main objectives (Section 2) of the project in terms of communication, dissemination and exploitation, as well as the methodology (Section 3) and key channels (Section 6) that will be exploited in order to reach out to the target stakeholders throughout the project duration. Early achievements and outputs from the first five months of project activity are also listed, providing tangible examples for the work to come. Target stakeholders are described in Section 4, and more details about them will be included in the upcoming analysis by BioDT Work Package 8 - Collaboration and Integration with Strategic Initiatives and Programmes.

An initial description of the exploitation and sustainability model is included in Section 7, while specific work on this officially begins in Year 2 under Task 2.4 - Sustainability.

An overview of the KPIs as of month 5 is featured in Section 8, providing an early snapshot of the project progress regarding communication, dissemination and exploitation.

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1. Introduction

The BioDT project will provide both advanced models for simulation and prediction capabilities, via eight thematic use cases to address critical issues related to global biodiversity dynamics, in support of the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 to protect nature and reverse the degradation of ecosystems.

The project involves four leading biodiversity research infrastructures (GBIF, eLTER, DiSSCo and LifeWatch ERIC) in the co-creation of the Biodiversity Digital Twin (BioDT) prototypes, strengthening the research infrastructures existing operational services and creating new opportunities for novel uses of their resources.

The BioDT WP2 - Communication, Dissemination, Sustainability and Impact ensures outreach beyond the specific consortium network towards the wider community of stakeholders, end-users, and general public. The project will achieve its communication and dissemination objectives through a widely tested and trustworthy methodology.

This deliverable presents an initial stakeholder analysis – which complements the work focusing on strategic initiatives and programmes foreseen in WP8 – as well as the key elements of the communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy and plan that will be carried out in the three years of the project.

Early achievements and outputs from the first five months of activity within WP2 are also listed, providing tangible examples for the work to come.

All the completed engagement activities and achievements will be described in Deliverable 2.2 Final plan dissemination & exploitation including communication activities, scheduled for month 35.

2. Main Objectives

The WP2 acts as the main link between the project and the outside world. In coordination with the more specific interactions carried out in WP7 (requirements gathering and training among users) and WP8 (coordination with other initiatives), WP2 leads the development, update and implementation of the communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy for BioDT.

The main objectives of the DEC activities are as follows:

- Transfer BioDT knowledge and results to relevant stakeholder groups
- Raise awareness and openly demonstrate clear economic, social, and technological benefits of employing BioDT solutions in the biodiversity community
- Maximise the impact of research and enable the value of results to go beyond BioDT and its immediate end users.

Through the activities described in this deliverable, WP2 will stimulate outreach towards different types of stakeholders and enhance the impact of project results beyond the consortium boundaries to promote uptake and innovation, in support of the overall objectives:

- Build and deploy a pre-operational BioDT for addressing biodiversity dynamics
- Support the interoperability of data and services through the integration of the BioDT with research infrastructure platforms and workflows
- Ensure interoperability of the BioDT with Destination Earth, and the European Data Infrastructure.

3. Methodology

The BioDT Communication Methodology and Stakeholder Journey (see Figure 1) ensures that each communication and dissemination activity is connected to the goals of the project.

Communication and dissemination activities are included in the Attract – Convert – Close – Delight – Promote process. This ensures a logical transition from **Stranger**, someone who is not familiar with the project, to **Visitor**, someone who interacts with the digital content, to **Lead**, a BioDT target stakeholder who has shown interest in what the project communicates and explicitly requested BioDT to engage with them, to **User/Provider**, a stakeholder who has directly responded to BioDT initiatives, used BioDT services and practically interacted with the project in a tangible manner, and finally to **Promoter**, a stakeholder who is so pleased with their interactions with BioDT that they are happy to promote the outputs, services and results of the project.

This process ensures an interconnected and efficient communications and engagement ecosystem.

Measuring feedback meaningfully through KPIs can be achieved by organising important phases of the project such as the release of use cases, or the launch of a hackathon.

Figure 1 – Stakeholder journey

4. Stakeholder Analysis

BioDT has identified four main stakeholder groups (SGs) that can benefit directly and indirectly from the main results of the project:

1. Biodiversity RIs, RI nodes, data providers and researchers;
2. Policy Makers;
3. Industrial actors and SMEs;
4. Civil society and citizen scientists.

The following sections present a short description of each SG and the targeted communication and dissemination strategy to engage with them and ensure they are aware of the latest developments of BioDT and uptake opportunities.

4.1 Biodiversity RIs, RI Nodes, Data Providers and Researchers

This SG includes research infrastructures, universities, research organisations, which represent the end-users that are going to contribute to the DT development, to enhance the use cases and test the DT functionalities.

This SG is crucial for BioDT as it currently encounters difficulties in collecting and accessing data in different infrastructures. This is driven by the fact that many RIs do not share common data model standards to facilitate data processing and analysis. This status quo prevents RIs, RI nodes, data providers and researchers from accessing and developing new services efficiently. The cooperation between BioDT and this target group is going to improve the quality of services offered by RIs, data providers and researchers. BioDT has already started this process by establishing joint efforts with four RIs operating in biodiversity, namely DiSSCo, LifeWatch ERIC, GBIF and eLTER.

In order to further engage with RIs, RI nodes (nodes as in primarily national hubs/facilities of the RIs), data providers and researchers, the BioDT team is going to organise trainings and technical workshops, such as the Bring Your Own Data and Bring Your Own Model, planned respectively for project month 18 and month 28. The participation in these events helps this SG to familiarise with the use of the Digital Twin services, data, and models. The publication of scientific papers by the BioDT team helps this target group also to better understand the state of the art of the DTs development.

4.2 Policy Makers

Policy makers represent Governments and the public sector, including EU Member States, local governments and intergovernmental organisations, that need appropriate tools to perform reliable, comprehensive and timely analyses and implement data-driven decisions to protect and restore biodiversity.

Cooperating with BioDT helps policy makers to make informed decisions based on quality data and modelling, addressing societal needs that are at the core of relevant policy strategies and initiatives, like the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030 and the UN Sustainable Development Goals.

BioDT is going to engage with this SG in particular through the development of four policy papers, which include medium and long-term recommendations for the employment of the digital twins developed in BioDT. The policy papers are based on the studies conducted by the four BioDT use cases groups. The engagement is going to be further strengthened through the participation to third-party events, such as the ones organised by Destination Earth, EOSC or EuroHPC environments.

4.3 Industrial Actors and SMEs

One of the goals of BioDT is to exploit its advanced technologies for business solutions to industrial actors that operate in biodiversity, such as agri-food, tourism, or healthcare.

This target group lacks innovative modelling solutions to implement optimised strategies that bring business results with low negative impact on biodiversity. The studies conducted by the BioDT use cases help to better understand industrial needs and the barriers that prevent this group from adopting such solutions.

Hence, the collaboration with BioDT brings the opportunity to co-develop with industrial actors and SMEs and advance RI technologies that facilitate technology transfer in this sector. Moreover, the cooperation also

brings the opportunity to further explore new business sectors to develop and adopt new applications and products.

BioDT is going to engage with industrial actors through technology transfer to create new applications and data spaces to explore new Research and Development solutions.

4.4 Civil Society and Citizen Scientists

Civil society and citizen scientists are willing to contribute to biodiversity-related research but are often lacking the tools to understand the value of the data they collect and its impact on research.

The adoption of BioDT solutions will strengthen common understanding of biodiversity dynamics and prediction models contributing to have an impact also on policy making. In this way, citizens can better understand the value of biodiversity literacy and overall that of biodiversity research.

BioDT is going to engage with citizens through dedicated sessions at citizen science-related events, and through the EOSC network. Interactive tools, such as Zooinverse.org and WeObserve, will be shared with citizen science projects across Europe to highlight the need for new data.

5. Strategy

BioDT will update its strategy for outreach, dissemination and exploitation during the evolution of the project. Interaction with stakeholders will provide the input and feedback for how and where BioDT needs to evolve given the key developments of the results and ensuring they are known to target audiences. Based on the different phases in the stakeholder journey specific channels will be used for two-way interaction for the different stages.

BioDT has identified a series of Key Exploitable Results (KERs), constituting the centre of the project's communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy. These KERs are further explained in Section 7 Exploitation and Sustainability Model.

- BioDT KER #1 Asset: Digital Twin Platform – TRL Initial 4, Final 7
- BioDT KER #2 Asset: Data modelling & simulation frameworks - TRL Initial 4, Final 8
- BioDT KER #3 Asset: Use Cases - TRL Initial 3, Final 7
- BioDT KER #4 Asset: Integration APIs - TRL Initial 4, Final 7
- BioDT KER #5 Asset: FAIR data design - TRL Initial 6, Final 8
- BioDT KER #6 Asset: Policy papers
- BioDT KER #7 Asset: Training - TRL Initial 6, Final 9

5.1 Communication Strategy

Communication takes place throughout the entire duration of the project under the lead of WP2, with active contributions from relevant partners also involved in other WPs for the production of technical content, feedback collection, participation in events.

The strategy mainly covers the first two steps of the stakeholder journey highlighted in Section 3, involving a variety of channels aimed at awareness raising, promotion of the project journey, outreach to the wider public, described in detail in Section 6.

5.2 Dissemination Strategy

Dissemination is executed in parallel with communication, ramping up after the first year of the project, where some tangible results can be shown and tested by target communities, and especially in the second half of the project.

This element mostly covers engaged stakeholders, in the more advanced stages of the journey, and requires their active involvement via dedicated channels that are described in Section 6.

5.3 Exploitation Strategy

The joint exploitation plans mostly revolve around sustaining the integrated BioDT platform, its components and major outputs as central to the future sustainability strategy. More details can be found in the dedicated Section 7. Work on these aspects takes place in Years 2 and 3 of the project.

6. Communication, Dissemination, Stakeholder Engagement and Exploitation Plan

The plan involves specific channels for communication and dissemination that are employed to achieve different goals and engage different targets, listed and described in the following subsections. After an overview of the channels, initial achievements as of month 5 are added as examples in Section 6.3.

6.1 Channels for Communication Activities

Project outreach is achieved via a range of different channels, which cater to different needs and situations. They are used to attract specific types of viewers and ignite their stakeholder journey.

6.1.1 Website

The BioDT website (<https://www.biodt.eu/>) acts as the main showcase for all project results and information, thematically arranged. It was released in its initial form by the third month of the project and is going to be expanded with all necessary sections in the upcoming months, including:

- Descriptions of the research infrastructures involved in the project
- Detailed descriptions of the use cases
- An overview of the interactions with other initiatives in the Destination Earth ecosystem and other communities (e.g. EOSC)
- FAQ page with most important questions coming from webinars/other channels

At every website iteration, a structured process is followed within the BioDT WP2 lead organisation Trust-IT Srl and affiliated entity COMMpla Srl to guarantee the best results, as displayed in Figure 2. The marketing team provides a first draft of the website structure and looks based on the main project goals, following UX principles. The graphic team applies their experience to elaborate a visually attractive mockup, while the technical team is involved in the later implementation and testing phases where the process goes back to the marketing team for feedback. When necessary, the FIGMA platform is used for the mock-up phases for better interaction between teams.

Figure 2 – Website development process

6.1.2 Social Media

Social media channels play a central role in the public communication activities for BioDT, reaching out well beyond professionals and researchers. Biodiversity is a topic of conversation also in terms of social interest and the project will exploit relevant opportunities across a range of channels.

BioDT uses the following social media channels: Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube, all characterised by the coordinated branding as explained in the dedicated Section 6.3.1.

Figure 3 – BioDT social media headers

6.1.2.1 Twitter

The Twitter account @BiodiversityDT (<https://twitter.com/BiodiversityDT>) is the channel mainly used for quick and general communication about the project as well as the most frequently updated (with 2 to 3 tweets per week), through captivating visuals and to-the-point messaging.

The project will especially exploit popular hashtags such as #biodiversity, #EUBiodiversity, and the ones related to the different use case topics ranging from #zerohunger and #sdgs to #pollinators and #climatechange.

Live tweeting at webinars, workshops, or other physical events is another important pillar of BioDT's presence on this channel, as it helps make the feed more dynamic and allows different users to find out about the project. This is generally done with at least one tweet per each speaker during relevant sessions, capturing the key messages and eventually pointing to related content on the BioDT platform.

6.1.2.2 LinkedIn

LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/biodt>) is particularly useful to reach out to researchers and professionals in the field. The possibility to tag, among others, partners, leaders, researchers and guest speakers with their professional profile increases the chances of visibility within their respective networks, allowing BioDT to reach related audiences and potentially new users and/or promoters. This channel is usually updated with 1 to 2 posts per week, depending on the needs of the project.

Aside from communicating project advancements and disseminating results, LinkedIn is also especially useful for promoting open positions in the project, related to the BioDT journey. Partners are invited to make use of the BioDT channels also for these purposes.

6.1.2.3 YouTube

The BioDT YouTube channel (<https://www.youtube.com/@biodt9048>) is used to host three main types of contents, which can then also be reused on other platforms via sharing or embedding:

- Interviews
- Recordings of webinars, or other events
- Tutorials and explanation videos

Visibility is also attained thanks to suggestions in the "related videos" via the use of relevant keywords in the fields of biodiversity and digital twins for titles and descriptions. Videos can then also lead to relevant content on the website.

6.1.3 Articles and Press Releases

Press releases are prepared and published to accompany key turning points in the lifetime of the project, as in the case of the kick-off meeting, the availability of a beta release, and others. These are then distributed across the consortium for publication on official platforms, as well as to relevant actors in the field, so as to maximise visibility and outreach.

Simpler articles are also produced for the website to follow the general evolution of the project, or other important activities, such as reporting on webinars and other relevant events.

6.1.4 Newsletters

The project newsletter is published quarterly on the second Tuesday of the month, unless there are special needs from the project. The newsletter features the most relevant updates for the community, serving as a key channel for reaching out to already interested contacts who decided to sign up.

Newsletters are sent via Mailchimp, and are agreed upon after collecting information from WP2 as well as eventual recommendations from other WPs.

The issues are expected to feature three to five different topics, covering news, events, vacancies, and other types of relevant information.

6.1.5 Multimedia Materials

BioDT will explore different types of multimedia content, ranging from photos to visuals, but especially videos and podcasts.

6.1.5.1 Videos

Videos provide highly engaging content, and make it easier for those who do not want (or do not have the time) to read through complex material to get a better understanding of the project. As mentioned in Section 6.1.2.3, there will be different types.

- Interviews – project representatives or guest speakers will be featured in brief interviews (less than 4-minute long) on specific topics, to be easily shared through the project channels. At least 10 video interviews are going to be delivered within the project lifetime.
- Recordings of webinars, or other events – these will allow our stakeholders to re-watch or watch past sessions.
- Tutorials and explanation videos – this type of video can be particularly useful for end-users themselves, featuring experts from the BioDT consortium that will explain how to use project results, making for relevant training materials.
- Only if budget allows it, there is the possibility of adding extra thematic documentaries during the second half of the project, if specific use cases need them to better describe their work to a non-technical audience.

Each video is expected to reach 500 organic views across platforms as of the end of the project, while sponsored videos in the second half of the project are expected to reach 2 000 views each.

6.1.5.2 Podcasts

The project will also carry out audio interviews with representatives of thematic user communities, a total of 4, to represent the four different use case groups. These will be presented as podcast episodes. The episodes can feature either one or more guests, depending on the specific topic, and will tackle both practical and more domain-specific issues.

Podcasts will be hosted on an easily accessible platform – such as Anchor – allowing other potential end-users to hear directly from their peers about the benefits of BioDT.

In order to be more relevant and based on advanced results, podcast episodes will be recorded and published in Year 3 of the project.

6.2 Channels for Dissemination of Results

BioDT aims to maximise the visibility and awareness of the project and widely disseminate its outcomes and research findings. In order to achieve this, the dissemination plan will focus on the following activities aimed at helping to increase visibility, recognition and awareness of the project.

- Engagement with stakeholders through webinars;
- Organisation of workshops, technical conferences, Hackathon and Summer schools;
- Participation in third-party events;
- Publication of scientific papers;
- Establishing synergies with relevant initiatives in the field of HPC, biodiversity, Open Science.

6.2.1 Webinars

Webinars are central to enable a smooth transition from physical events to virtual events and offer the chance of presenting cutting-edge results of BioDT.

The main strategic goals of the webinars are linked to the promotion of the BioDT objectives, its use cases, its technical work to deliver the prototype digital twins, and the cooperation established with relevant players in HPC, biodiversity, or RIs environments.

Throughout the BioDT project lifespan, the project team is going to organise a total of 10 webinars to highlight the progress of the above-mentioned topics. A draft plan of the times and topics covered by each online event is provided in the table below.

Number	Month	Topic of the webinar
1	M02 (July 2022)	General overview of the project
2	M04 (September 2022)	General presentation of the use cases
3	M11 (April 2023)	Presentation of Use Case Group 1
4	M13 (June 2023)	Presentation of Use Case Group 2
5	M18 (November 2023)	Presentation of Use Case Group 3
6	M20 (January 2024)	Presentation of Use Case Group 4
7	M23 (April 2024)	Cooperation with synergies
8	M25 (June 2024)	Presentation of the BioDT services
9	M28 (September 2024)	Presentation of the final developments of the use cases
10	M33 (February 2025)	Presentation of the digital twin

Table 1 – Webinar plan

Promotional, outreach and dissemination activities spanning through the pre- and post-webinars are going to be implemented for all the webinars:

- Creation of standardised and branded graphics;
- Set-up of a dedicated registration page on the BioDT website;
- Tailored email campaign to reach out relevant stakeholders;
- Social media regular activity;
- Live tweeting during the event;
- Upload and release of the recorded webinar on YouTube and on the BioDT website;
- Upload of the speakers' presentations on Zenodo and the BioDT website;
- Post-event "thank you message" addressing participants;
- Post-webinar report published on the website and Zenodo;
- Content published on social media in the following weeks.

6.2.2 Technical Conferences, Workshops and Other Third-party Events

Technical conferences and workshops are often linked to event proceedings or peer-reviewed papers. Especially for RIA projects, they represent important means to confirm results and enhance the reputation of contributing authors in the field.

The strategy to be adopted to showcase the main scientific developments to BioDT is summarised in the Table 2 below.

Objectives	Activities	Sample events / workshops	Timeline
Widely broadcasting BioDT at top-notch scientific venues as the basis for reputation-building within the	Presentations, peer reviewed paper submission, technical posters	FAIR Data Conference, ISC HPC, High Performance Computing Conference, EHPCSW, IEEE Conference on Digital Twins, Science Europe Open Science Conference	M01-M36

biodiversity, digital twin communities			
Showcasing mature results at international trade fairs, industry and B2B events, start-up playgrounds, including virtual events	Demos, adoption info and marketing packages for end-users	Digital Twin Conference, Digital Twin Forum, MMLDT-CSET, Digital Twin Days, TwinNets	M18-M36

Table 2 – Strategy to get visibility through technical conferences and workshops

Third-party events

Participation in third-party events serves several purposes depending on the exact scope and purpose of the specific event:

- Sharing BioDT insights, knowledge, technical and non-technical results;
- Gaining an understanding of the digital twin technology landscape, including advances in peer-project, other EU and international research. This may also include joint dissemination with peer projects;
- Getting insights into market needs and business adoption plans;
- Communicating the focus and benefits of BioDT;
- Increasing BioDT visibility;
- Extending the BioDT network, including developer communities. Over time, it will also be important to be active at events that are important for exploitation and sustainability in terms of uptake.

Third-party event participation is driven around their timeliness with BioDT outputs, topic and audience relevance and will increasingly prioritise events that offer an opportunity to showcase mature results, from a technical perspective.

Participation in third-party events spans presentations, panel debates, promotional stands, poster displays, remote participation and the distribution of project promotional material (such as roll-up banners, flyers) for focused and effective communication, dissemination and engagement outcomes, with live reporting via twitter, updates and posts on social media channels. The participation in third-party events will also involve sharing takeaways and follow-up actions with the consortium and periodically with advisers, tracking impacts as part of the innovation management. This also applies to events hosted by BioDT.

For events planning, the consortium will define, through a shared online events document available to all partners, what events represent the best opportunity for the project. This online file will include at least:

- Who is going to attend, where and when;
- What is going to be presented (overview of presentation/topic);
- Type of audience that will join the event;
- What graphical material and details for shipping is needed.

As part of the communications plan WP2 takes care of the following activities in order to provide additional visibility to the project:

- Timely publishing of the event on the website;
- Publishing the presentation slides;
- Setting up a dedicated Social Media campaign.

6.2.3 Summer School

Summer schools are courses provided by a university of research institution to university students or any other interested stakeholders. The courses are meant to be informative training and classes that can be organised online, physically or in a hybrid form. The name of this school comes to the fact that this training is mainly organised during the summer time, a period when students and professors have more free time and can dedicate it to explore new topics.

The summer schools are an engaging instrument to let researchers, RIs and ICT players gather innovative insights in terms of biodiversity digital twins and increase their knowledge through lectures with teachers that might come from an external network. As a matter of fact, summer schools allow students to expand their educational community and interact with European and international research groups.

The BioDT WP7 and WP2 teams are going to organise a summer school in M34 (March 2025). The workshop will be organised almost at the end of the project to allow the BioDT stakeholders to test the prototype DTs constructed during the project at the latest stages of development for better understanding and assessment.

The BioDT summer school is going to be delivered online through interactive and recorded lessons, available via LifeWatch ERIC. The publication of the training online helps increase the adoption of the biodiversity digital twin and reach a wider scientific community.

6.2.4 Hackathon

Hackathons are physical or digital events where experts get together over a short period of time to cooperate together on a project. The aim of these events is to let experts test the technological prototypes in advance and provide feedback.

The BioDT WP4 – Data and Use Cases is in charge of the organisation of Bring Your Own Data (BYOD) and Bring Your Own Model (BYOM) hackathons to reach out to the communities beyond the consortium to let them quickly familiarise on the use of the digital twin services, data, and model.

The targeted communities invited to join are the ones related to life science, marine, and climate science environments.

6.2.5 Scientific Publications

The scientific contribution of BioDT will produce several technical papers, published and distributed through peer-reviewed journals, some of which will be presented at different kinds of conferences and will be further utilised for dissemination. The number of total publications delivered by the team is continuously monitored by the WP2 team with the supervision of the Coordinator of the BioDT project.

The BioDT Consortium is committed to open data repositories and journals. For this purpose, the project has already created a Zenodo account (<https://zenodo.org/communities/biodt>), a joint repository that is part of the OpenAIRE service operated by the EC. In addition to this, individual partners will also use repositories available at their respective institutions to enhance the dissemination of the scientific publications. Where possible, gold open-access options will be targeted, in which the publisher makes the publication available as open access or will target green open-access options through self-archive by making publications available in an online repository after publication (a suitable budget has been allocated for gold open access). BioDT will also make available all the experimental data, including application logs and training data sets, thereby ensuring its reproducibility and sharing of research results.

In order to keep track of the publications developed by the project members and make them aware of all documents that are being prepared, under review or being accepted, the BioDT team has elaborated a manuscript template. The overall purpose of the manuscript is to ensure that the publication plan is communicated to the entire consortium and tracked in a dedicated file. In this way, the entire project team can be aware of the diverse topics of different publications. In particular, the authors of each scientific paper include in the shared document a short overview of the people that have contributed to the paper, topic,

DOI, status of the publication. Based on these details, WP2 communicates the manuscript overview and key questions to the consortium, so that all project members have a concept of which papers are currently in development; keep the consortium up-to-date on the status of individual manuscripts and maintain records of publications for continuous reporting, as part of wider continuous reporting activities.

6.2.6 Channels for Reaching Stakeholders

BioDT can tap into a wide pool of associations and partner networks to build synergies and reach the targeted stakeholders at the primary, secondary and tertiary levels.

The table below presents the diverse topics relevant for BioDT. These strong network links cover many relevant targeted end-users and stakeholders, spanning from biodiversity to digital twins. The pool of network will help BioDT to build its community database as part of its strategy for stakeholder engagement.

Topic	Samples of organisations to engage with	BioDT partner
Research data, digital services	RIs	CSC, RIs
Biodiversity	Universities (i.e. Wageningen)	Use Case partners
High-performance computing	LUMI, EuroHPC	CSC, IT4I@VSB
EU science data	EOSC Association	CSC, Trust-IT
FAIR data management	Fair Digital Objects	Naturalis
Destination Earth	EU – DestinE board, EMWCF, ESA	CSC, TNO, ECMWF
Ocean and interoperability	BioFlow / eDTO / DiTTo / Turtle	TNO
Twin best practices	OMG-DTC	TNO
Biodiversity policies	EU Environmental Agency, EU Biodiversity Policy 2030, National Biodiversity policies	RIs

Table 3 – Sample of relevant organisations

Moreover, the BioDT strategy taps into a pool of multipliers that can help create a snowball effect across broader communities.

Multiplier networks
Associations linked to Biodiversity RIs, data providers and researchers: @NFDI4BioDiv, @BExplo_research, @CopernicusLand, @eurotaxonomy, @evoltreeNW, @porbiota, @CIBIO_InBIO, @CECT_UV, @RJBOTANICO, @BccmCollections, @INBOVlaanderen, @RBINSmuseum, @AgroBRC_RARe, @INRAE, @latjitiето, @EOSC-Life, @ENVRIcomm, @ELIXIREurope
Associations relevant for Policy makers: @UNBiodiversity, @unepwcmc, @Biodiversity_be, @OFBiodiversite, @OECD_ENV, @IPBES, @GEOSEC2025, @EUClimateAction, @EUgreenresearch, @LIFEprogramme, @ BiodivERsA, OISPG - Open Innovation Strategy and Policy Group.
Industrial actors and SMEs: @EUROPARC, @OrganicsEurope, European Green Digital Coalition, @WeValueNature, @EEN_EU, @CapsCoalition, @epe_asso, Biodiversity in Good Company, @valuebalancing, @ProBiodiversity, @biconsortium
Associations relevant for Civil society and citizen scientists: @Green_Europe, @SDG2030, @WWF, @FAO, @FSC_IC, @ReinforceEU, @WeObserveEU, @LandSense, @growobservatory, @CSEOLab, @SCENT_EU
Multipliers linked to relevant initiatives such as EOSC, digital twins, EuroHPC, etc.: @EoscPortal, @EuroHPC_JU, @eoscassociation, @EOSCFuture, @BioExcelCOE, @esiwace, @EUScienceInnov,

@DataEcoEU, @HorizonEU, @ScienceEurope, @PRACE_RI, @EOSC-Nordic, @EOSC-Pillar, GAIA-X, UK Digital Twin Programme

News and media portals related to research and biodiversity: @ResearchEurope, @scibus, @CORDIS_EU, @agrochemie, @biobasedpress, @guardianeco, @BBCEarth, @EUEnvironment, @euronewsgreen

Table 4 – Multiplier networks

6.3 Achievements and Impacts to Date

6.3.1 Branding

Over the course of the first six months from the project launch, a complete brand image of BioDT has been prepared. The project branding aims to ensure a consistent and distinctive look and feel across various communication channels spanning from social media, printing and web platforms with the creation of branded posters, fliers, website banners, web platform graphics, presentations template, and a deliverable template.

The branding includes the development of the BioDT logo, available in six different colour versions to make the project recognisable. The logo is used in all communication and dissemination activities of BioDT. Moreover, in order to make the project look recognisable and professional at the same time, the project team has also developed a branded PowerPoint template, banners that were published on the social media channels and a Zoom background used during virtual presentations.

Some of the branded materials are visible in the figures below:

Figure 4 – BioDT logo pack

Figure 5 – BioDT social media header

Figure 6 – BioDT PPT template

Figure 7 – BioDT video conference background

6.3.1.1 Collaterals

In addition to the branding materials, the BioDT team has also developed collaterals to make the project recognisable at public events.

The two types of collaterals developed by the team in the first six months from the BioDT launch are a roll-up banner and a flyer.

The roll-up banner is a self-standing graphic advertising banner that presents the main goals, outcomes and partners of BioDT. The roll-up banner is printed only on one side and has generally the dimensions of 850mm x 2000mm. The roll-up banner developed for BioDT has been printed on recycled paper and used to showcase the project at the kick-off meeting.

Figure 8 – BioDT roll-up banner

The flyer is a small piece of paper, generally with the dimensions of an A4 document, printed on both sides that presents with short and effective sentences the main objectives of the project. The BioDT flyer has been finalised in October 2022 to present the project at international events, like the SC22 in Dallas, USA. The flyer is available on a printable and online version to reduce the physical copies needed at events and is generally printed in the city where the event takes place to reduce the CO₂ impact connected to transportation.

Figure 9 – BioDT flyer

6.3.2 Website

A first simple version of the website was already available by the project kick-off meeting in June 2022, and several basic pages were added by month 3, including a contact form for users to get in touch with project representatives.

Figure 10 – BioDT home page

As of the time of writing this document, the website is structured as listed below:

Figure 11 – BioDT website structure

6.3.3 Social Media Channels

As of the end of month 5 (October 2022), BioDT social media channels have already achieved some visibility. Relevant statistics for the first 5 months can be found below:

Channel	Metric	Value as of M05
Twitter	Total followers	279
	Twitter impressions	57.8k impressions
	Tweets	50 (12 per month)
LinkedIn	Total followers	224

	LinkedIn Impressions	8k impressions
	Posts	24 (6 per month)
YouTube	Total followers	25
	Total views	585

Table 5 – Social media channels

6.3.4 Articles and Press Releases

The first dedicated press release was produced at the beginning of the project to accompany the kick-off meeting and divulge general information about the mission of BioDT.

The press release was published on 10 June 2022 on the BioDT website¹.

Title	Date	Views on BioDT M05	Other websites
BioDT: a Digital Twin prototype to help protect and restore biodiversity	10 June 2022	413	CSC Trust-IT ELTER GBIF DiSSCo

Table 6 – Articles and Press Releases

6.3.5 Newsletters

The newsletter proved extremely successful already in the first five months of the project, with our initial KPI target of 350 subscribers already achieved after the first two webinars. Because of this, we are going to consider 800 subscribers as the M36 target, as also shown in Section 8.

Title	Date	Deliveries	Open rate
A Digital Twin prototype to help protect and restore biodiversity ²	13 Sep 2022	269	43.1%

Table 7 – Newsletters

Newsletters are sent every three months, and the next one is scheduled for 13 December 2022. A specific page has been added to the website, where past newsletters are going to be collected³.

6.3.6 Videos

A series of interviews with Work Package leaders were carried out at the kick-off meeting in June 2022, focusing on the main points of interest for each WP. Specific ones were also used to promote the two webinars on social media over the first months, as explained in Section 6.3.7 below.

¹ <https://biodt.eu/news/biodt-digital-twin-prototype-help-protect-and-restore-biodiversity>

² <https://biodt.eu/newsletter-post/issue-1-digital-twin-prototype-help-protect-restore-biodiversity>

³ <https://biodt.eu/newsletter-posts>

<https://www.biodt.eu/>

Video title	Type	Publication date	Views per channel as of M05	Total views
Digital twinning to predict how biodiversity responds to global change - Jesse Harrison, CSC	Interview	05/07/2022	85 on YouTube 263 on Twitter 251 on LinkedIn	599
How will the LUMI Supercomputer contribute to BioDT goals? - An interview with Aleks Kallio, CSC	Interview	07/07/2022	38 on YouTube 205 on Twitter 306 on LinkedIn	549
Connecting BioDT with existing digital twins and data initiatives - Jeroen Broekhuijsen, TNO	Interview	12/07/2022	31 on YouTube 206 on Twitter 239 on LinkedIn	476
BioDT to help experts come together to implement FAIR principles - Sharif Islam, Naturalis	Interview	19/07/2022	19 on YouTube 359 on Twitter 101 on LinkedIn	479
Modelling approaches to predict biodiversity responses - Otso Ovaskainen, University of Jyväskylä	Interview	25/07/2022	28 on YouTube 1,762 on Twitter 104 on LinkedIn	1,894
Involve research infrastructures to integrate requirements & data - Tomáš Martinovič, IT4Innovations	Interview	28/07/2022	17 on YouTube 243 on Twitter 133 on LinkedIn	393
Enhancing BioDT's impact on the biodiversity research community - Federico Drago, Trust-IT	Interview	02/08/2022	21 on YouTube 116 on Twitter 74 on LinkedIn	211
Bringing together modelling and supercomputing power in BioDT use cases - Dmitry Schigel, GBIF	Interview	16/08/2022	63 on YouTube 415 on LinkedIn	478
We are going to tackle key challenges in biodiversity thanks to the Digital Twin - Dag Endresen, University of Oslo	Interview	18/08/2022	20 on YouTube 512 on Twitter 123 on LinkedIn	655
The Biodiversity Digital Twin: A new solution to support protection and restoration of ecosystems	Webinar recording	15/07/2022	159 on YouTube	159
BioDT use cases: unique demonstrators to test the biodiversity Digital Twin prototype	Webinar recording	28/09/2022	105 on YouTube	105

Table 8 – Videos

6.3.7 Events

In the first six months from the launch of the project, the BioDT team has organised two webinars. The first one took place on 13 July 2022 and was entitled "**The Biodiversity Digital Twin: a new solution to support protection and restoration of ecosystems**". The second one, "**The BioDT use cases: unique demonstrators to test the biodiversity Digital Twin prototype**", took place on 27 September 2022.

The table below provides a snapshot of the webinars in terms of date and number of participants.

Webinar title	Date	Number of participants
The Biodiversity Digital Twin: a new solution to support protection and restoration of ecosystems	13/07/2022	122
The BioDT use cases: unique demonstrators to test the biodiversity Digital Twin prototype	27/09/2022	93

Table 9 – Webinars

In order to promote the webinar, dedicated web pages with a registration form were created and SMART social media campaigns were performed. SMART campaigns refer to communication activities that are specific, measurable, achievable, realistic, time-bound. Dates are set for the campaign launch, mid-term impact monitoring and impacts at the end of the campaign.

- **The Biodiversity Digital Twin: a new solution to support protection and restoration of ecosystems - main outcomes**

The first webinar took place on 13 July 2022 and gave the opportunity to the participants to learn more about the objectives and goals of the project, and its interaction with the LUMI Supercomputer, fundamental for building its modelling and simulation capabilities.

The event was structured into **3 main parts**:

1. An introduction to the BioDT project and its main goals;
2. An interactive session with the audience to test their experience in the biodiversity field and increase the engagement level during the event;
3. A panel discussion on challenges and priorities faced by biodiversity in the context of climate change.

The full **agenda** and all the information about the **event** and the related **registration link** were added to a **dedicated page** on the BioDT website.

The webinar was promoted through the main BioDT **social media channels** and, thanks to a cooperative effort of the entire team, it gained **197 registrants** and was attended by **122 people**, showing a **62% attendance rate**. The attendees were mainly coming from Europe, but the webinar proved to be interesting also for people living outside the European borders, like USA or Japan.

Figure 12 – Participants of the 1st BioDT webinar

As mentioned above, a SMART campaign has been launched to promote the webinar among relevant stakeholders. In this case, it ran from 28 June to 13 July 2022, gaining 1954 impressions on LinkedIn and 9147 on Twitter. Graphical examples developed for this purpose can be found below.

Figure 13 – Examples of the SMART campaign run for the 1st webinar

- **The BioDT use cases: unique demonstrators to test the biodiversity Digital Twin prototype - main outcomes**

The second webinar "**The BioDT use cases: unique demonstrators to test the biodiversity Digital Twin prototype**" took place on 27 September 2022 and presented the groups of use cases that showcase how BioDT can examine its predictive performance and address biodiversity challenges through scenario simulations, predictions and biomonitoring methods.

The event was structured into three main parts:

4. A short introduction of the BioDT use cases;
5. A presentation of the Group 2, 3 and 4 of the use cases;
6. An interactive session with the audience through menti.com followed by a Q&A session.

The full **agenda** and all the information about the **webinar** and the related **registration link** were added on an event page of the BioDT website.

Similarly to the first webinar, the use cases webinar was promoted through the main BioDT **social media channels** and, thanks to a cooperative effort of the entire team, it gained **137 registrants** and was attended by **93 people**, showing a **68% attendance rate**. The attendees were mainly coming from Europe but attendees from other continents appreciated the event as the webinar registered attendees also from the United States of America, Saudi Arabia, Uganda, Kenya, Egypt, Canada, Turkey and India.

Figure 14 – Participants of the 2nd BioDT webinar

Also for the 2nd webinar, the event was promoted following the principles of a SMART campaign, which was launched on 16 August and run until 27 September 2022. Thanks to the campaign, the posts gained 1488 impressions on LinkedIn and 12627 on Twitter. Graphical examples developed for this purpose can be found below.

Figure 15 – Examples of the SMART campaign run for the 2nd webinar

6.3.7.1 Third-party events

The team has also joined third-party events to present the main objectives and intermediary achievements of BioDT. The full list of third-party events joined by the team are presented below:

Event name	Date	Location	BioDT partner
OMG Digital Twin Consortium Member meeting Q3	27/09/2022	Leeds, United Kingdom	Jeroen Broekhuijsen (TNO)
Ocean Practices: OBPS Workshop VI	19/10/2022	Online	Jeroen Broekhuijsen (TNO)
1st International Conference on FAIR Digital Objects	26 - 28/10/2022	Leiden, the Netherlands	Sharif Islam (Naturalis)
International Conference on High Performance Computing 2022	13 - 18/11/2022	Dallas, USA	Samantha Wittke (CSC), Katerina Slaninova (IT4Innovations), Jan Martinovic (IT4Innovations)

Table 10 – Third-party events

6.3.8 Publications

As an essential element of dissemination of results, publications help to demonstrate advances beyond the state-of-the-art and validate research findings. In the following tables we report the papers accepted for publication, including peer-reviewed, open-access and non-peer-reviewed papers.

At the time of writing this deliverable, the following proceeding paper has been published. However, the team is planning to submit additional publications in the upcoming months to increase the scientific contribution of the project.

Title	Authors	Type of proceedings	Year of publication	Publisher
From data pipelines to FAIR data infrastructures: A vision for the new horizons of bio- and geodiversity data for scientific research	Sharif Islam (Naturalis), Claus Weiland, Wouter Addink	Conference Abstract	2022	RIO Journal

Table 11 – Publications

6.3.9 Links with Other Initiatives

Similar to BioDT, several other initiatives are working on either Biodiversity, Digital Twins, Research Infrastructures and digital developments in the EU. To ensure BioDT is compatible and interoperable with these initiatives, links have been established with them to establish the way of working, results and interfaces are aligned.

Initiatives / Programmes	Objective of the connection / engagement	Potential stakeholders acting as mediators
Destination Earth as programme (DestinE) - system (data lake and core service platform and DTS) to host digital replicas of Earth system	Technical integration / Technical choices alignment for system design and early testing	ECMWF esp. DestinE DT-Engine, DestinE Climate Adaptation DT, DestinE Extremes DT, EUMETSAT, ESA, Science Advisory Board
Ocean Digital Twin - Iliad - Integrated digital framework for comprehensive maritime data and information services	Technical integration / BioDT reuses models developed by ODT	Iliad project consortium, Netcompany-Intrasoft (ODT Iliad project coordinator), WavEC-Offshore Renewables (leads ODT Iliad co-design activities) EDITO, DiTTo
European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)- EOSC aims to develop a “Web of FAIR Data and services” for science in Europe.	Architecture of the BioDT is aligned with the EOSC developments / Proposed services can be fully integrated in the EOSC platform	EOSC Future project; EOSC-ESFRI Science clusters, EOSC Association, INFRAEOSC projects funded under Horizon Europe
European Data Spaces	Technical alignment / BioDT to align 1) Governance on data, 2) Services created with data based on existing core functional blocks and 3) standards used for interoperability	Data Spaces Alliance, Gaia-X and OpenDEI
European HPC Infrastructure: EuroHPC	Strategic alignment / BioDT to align with the EuroHPC roadmap and lessons-learned on the realisation of digital twins feed back to the EuroHPC ecosystem	EuroHPC JU, EuroHPC Governing Board (GB), EuroHPC Infrastructure Advisory and Research and Innovation Advisory Groups, Hosting Entities, ETP4HPC

Other Digital Twin projects - Looking at prototypes of DTs for interdisciplinary science and other domains	Information exchange, potential collaboration agreement	Mercator Ocean, DT – GEO, InterTwin, eBRAIN-Health, EU-OS, ISO, OMG-DTC
Biodiversity	Uptake of BioDT outputs, involvement in requirements gathering, participation in events	DiSSCo, LifeWatch, GBIF and eLTER and other RIs and initiatives operating in biodiversity

Table 12 – Other initiatives

7. Exploitation and Sustainability Model

7.1.1 BioDT Key Exploitable Results and Joint Exploitation

Looking at both reusable results and other elements that have potential to contribute for further work on research or innovation, BioDT has identified a series of key exploitable results (KERs) and outlined initial joint dissemination and exploitation measures as detailed below.

The joint exploitation plans mostly revolves around sustaining the integrated BioDT platform, its components and major outputs as central to the future sustainability strategy.

BioDT KER #1 Asset: Digital Twin Platform – TRL Initial 4, Final 7

Joint Exploitation Measures - Adoption guides, training sessions, presentations targeting scientific community to demonstrate the work produced in BioDT and share this way of work and thinking. Summer schools and webinars in order to increase the usage of BioDT prototype.

Joint Dissemination Measures - Scientific publications, web-based media (e.g. podcasts, newsletters), media coverage (newspapers, radio, TV, and video documentaries).

BioDT KER #2 Asset: Data modelling & simulation frameworks - TRL Initial 4, Final 8

Joint Exploitation Measures - Workshops to involve RI nodes in the development of new data types and domain models required for advancing the modelling solutions for the use cases. Exchange of capacity between nodes to enable the RI nodes across the network to work efficiently together with their data publishers to establish new and enhanced data streams.

Joint Dissemination Measures - Dedicated marketing packages on concrete benefits. Workshops for RI nodes will mostly be organized back-to-back with the annual RI nodes meetings and RI nodes seminar series and webinars.

BioDT KER #3 Asset: Use Cases - TRL Initial 3, Final 7

Joint Exploitation Measures - Dedicated workshops to develop, present, and pilot the Use Case outputs. Training and education sessions will be organised based on the Use Cases results in order to pave the way for BioDT service uptake

Joint Dissemination Measures - Scientific publications, tutorials, animated demonstrations, training software and courses to inform and involve the scientific community, industry and policy makers.

BioDT KER #4 Asset: Integration APIs - TRL Initial 4, Final 7

Joint Exploitation Measures - Promotion and distribution of APIs to pave the way for future sustainability of BioDT through its integration with EU Data Spaces, EOSC and the other DTs under Destination Earth.

Joint Dissemination Measures - Dedicated training events will be organised in order to increase users' competencies required to effectively run their data projects on the DT. Training will involve researchers, coders, data providers and RI nodes.

BioDT KER #5 Asset: FAIR data design - TRL Initial 6, Final 8

Joint Exploitation Measures - All data will be available via a trusted, FAIR data repository, accessible via open protocols. The methods, design and process of the use cases will be published as open access publications. Training materials (available in open access format) will be produced for RIs, and the wider research community detailing how to use the BioDT prototype.

Joint Dissemination Measures - Existing and established networks of natural science collections and biodiversity communities (such as CETAF, TDWG, SPNHC) will be used to exploit the value of BioDT use cases. Networks include mailing lists, periodic conferences, social media and other interactive channels (such as Slack).

BioDT KER #6 Asset: Policy papers

Joint Exploitation Measures - Research and development activities based on the outcomes of the use case will result in key recommendations and best practices that will be communicated to policy makers during specific meetings and events.

Joint Dissemination Measures - Dedicated marketing package and distribution both in printed and digital copy. Dedicated webinars and press releases.

BioDT KER #7 Asset: Training - TRL Initial 6, Final 9

Joint Exploitation Measures - A Summer School mainly addressing RIs and their research and ICT staff is planned by M34 with the aim of empowering practitioners in the use of BioDT as well as work on its scalability.

Joint Dissemination Measures - Training will be delivered online through interactive and recorded lessons, available via LifeWatch ERIC. RI nodes will receive capacity to multiply the dissemination of training materials (train-the-trainers model) and provide BioDT courses and direct end-user support to researchers in the respective country of the RI node.

Table 13 – BioDT KERs and joint exploitation plan

7.1.2 Complementary Paths to Exploitation

In addition to the joint planning and measures, BioDT foresees complementary and strategic paths to exploitation:

Detailed exploitation plans defined by each individual partner, in line with the business and research strategy of each partner.

- Strategic goal: Ensuring BioDT becomes an integral part of the business portfolios/institutional services for guaranteed availability for uptake beyond the project lifecycle.
- Measures to be taken: Innovation and IPR management; implementation of a go-to-market strategy. A commercialisation strategy will be defined and implemented in both cases.

Exploitation of the use cases

- Strategic goal: Using the Use Cases as a lever to bring onboard other RIs and increase the use of the BioDT prototype. Integrate the applications with other offerings such as the DestinE Core Service Platform.
- Measures to be taken: Large-scale marketing campaigns, video pills, workshops and training sessions.

7.1.3 Business and Sustainability Model

As exploitation and sustainability are long term processes and commitments, it is of utmost important to ensure that the continuation for development, implementation, operation and user interaction are planned systematically through the whole life cycle of a KER, and that funders, asset owners, operators and users get the maximum benefit for their investments and efforts.

For this reason, BioDT will further its analysis of the KERs identified, joint and complementary paths to exploitation with the development of a business model.

The Canvas approach will be used for this analysis to detail

- What is the problem to be solved
- What is the solution, and especially what are the KERs
- Who are users (and potential paying customers) and why they would like to use the KER (can be also a public funding body looking for societal impacts in Europe)
- What are competing solutions (or how the problem is solved today)
- What are the Unique Selling Points

Considering the multi-partner context and as the KERs and other outcomes of the project are mostly shared, e.g. the platform, which all partners or even external bodies aim use after the project, BioDT aims to plan for and agree on an ownership model and to develop early drafts of the related operative model and the cost structure where applicable. In case of a shared ownership of project results, organising a well-functioning operative model might not be straightforward. Regulations and rules between states and organisations vary, so to ensure wide participation, early planning is essential. Key issues to discuss at this stage:

- What is the actual service/solution to be delivered, and what it is not (the essential delivery the targeted service for users / customers)
- Who can perform these essential activities (multiple bodies might be needed)
- What is the cost of performing these activities (e.g. personnel, use of equipment, administration)
- Are there limitations to selling the service (public bodies especially), or co-operation between states
- What is the market potential (monetary, number of users etc.)
- IPR protection strategy
- Risk analysis
- Who are other users or who else gain benefits for the asset (e.g. EuroHPC, DestinE or EOSC)

Once the ownership model, and operative and business model will be planned together with project partners, these will further enrich the identified joint and complementary plans to exploitation and will be the basis for the sustainability model which will further look into aspects such as:

- Transfer of project results to operating body
- Integration/implementation with other infrastructures / offerings
- Continuous business planning (cost and income structure, targeted volumes, market and customer analysis, etc)
- Continuous resources planning (e.g. personnel, premises, equipment);
- Continuous search for funding (e.g. EU funding, national funding, sales, partnerships)
- Further development planning

The sustainability model for the BioDT will be developed in the second year of the project, drawing from requirements from the research infrastructures, use cases and the engagement with key strategic initiatives. It will build on the lessons learned from the introduction of the BioDT services into diverse environments and from their listing as part of the LUMI service portfolio. The model will also particularly leverage the existing arrangements at European level, especially related to the EuroHPC and Destination Earth, and from relevant activities across the project (notably WP7 and WP8).

It will assemble the business case for the future BioDT covering the following elements: funding sources, market assessment and business models, dealing with all relevant IPR aspects, operational and maintenance costs. The strategic goal is to sustain core, interdependent assets beyond the lifecycle of the project to enable widespread adoption by the biodiversity community covering also additional other domains such as Life Science, Marine ecology and Earth Sciences.

8. KPIs Measurements

The impact of all strategically important WP2 activities performed is measured through a core set of key performance indicators (KPIs) wherever they are quantifiable. A continuous activity of monitoring is carried out by Trust-IT as WP2 leader and shared with all partners. Qualitative metrics come into play whenever there is a need for a deeper analysis of the relevance of outcomes achieved.

The table below shows the end of project KPI targets and their status at month 5.

KPI	Value M05	Target M36
Tailored promotional materials for different target groups (Flyers, posters, infographics, etc.)	2	6
Podcasts (dedicated interviews with end-users)	0	4
Scientific publications Scientific papers (5-10 peer-reviewed manuscripts accepted for publication in journals) Oral and poster abstracts (40 presentations at conferences or other third-party events)	1	50
Website releases	1	3
Number of authenticated /validated users achieved through the outreach events, (webinars, workshops, training, summer school, final event)	215	500+
Newsletters	1	12
Newsletters subscriptions	380	350+ (new proposed KPI 800)
Press releases (impressions on traditional media 3)	1	4
Webinars	2, with 107 average attendees	10 with average attendance of 40 participants
Videos	9 Video interviews	10 Video interviews
Videos visualisation	585 total organic views on YouTube	2000 sponsored video 500 organic video
Social media channels and campaigns	528 combined followers	1.500 combined social media followers

Use case workshops + training sessions	1 workshop 93 webinar attendees	8 with average attendance of 60 participants
RI nodes coordination workshops	0	2 events
Summer school	0	1 event
Third-party events	4	> 40 Presence events
Bring Your Own Data event	0	2 events
Policy Papers	0	4
Final event with Destination Earth	0	1 joint event

Table 14 – KPIs as of M05

9. Conclusions and Next Steps

With roots firmly grounded in the DEC plan described above, BioDT will grow into a prominent initiative, connecting communities across biodiversity, HPC, digital twinning, Open Science, exploiting the consortium strong links with the surrounding ecosystem and the possibility of cross-disciplinary interaction.

In particular, BioDT acts in the framework of key EU and international policy initiatives, including the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030, EU Green Deal, UN Sustainable Development Goals, Destination Earth.

Achieving our target KPIs will help BioDT make an impact among the key stakeholder groups identified in this document. The completion of the stakeholder journey described in Section 3 for as many people as possible will contribute to reaching BioDT's objectives, improving the chances for wider adoption across scientific communities.

2023 is going to be a fundamental year for the project as technical developments progress and use cases are further refined. DEC activities will showcase the evolution across the work packages, including the first wave of training activities (WP7) and the initial alignments with related initiatives (WP8).